

SITE	YEAR	AREA	SECTOR	ELEVATION	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT
GPR	11	B		Min: 62.1087 Max: 62.7354	1388 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Natural <input type="checkbox"/> Anthropic

In cross-section? Yes No In elevation drawing? Yes No Photos: Yes No #: 1724-1725 Photo Model: Yes No #:

DEFINITION: SOIL ABOVE ROAD/PAVEMENT Covered by SU: 1320 Fills SU: Filled by SU:

HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? Color Composition Compaction FORMATION PROCESS: Accumulation Construction Cutting Erosion Collapse Intentional deposition

INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are

Anthropic	Geological	Organic	SOIL/MATRIX
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pottery R <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Tiles C <input type="checkbox"/> Amphorae <input type="checkbox"/> Dolia <input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic tile(s) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Mortar R <input type="checkbox"/> Coins <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Metal (specify) R <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse debris <input type="checkbox"/> Glass	<input type="checkbox"/> Tufo (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Travertine <input type="checkbox"/> Other Limestone <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt <input type="checkbox"/> Clay <input type="checkbox"/> Sand <input type="checkbox"/> Silt <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pebbles (range) Small R <input type="checkbox"/> Gravel (range)	<input type="checkbox"/> Charcoal <input type="checkbox"/> Ash <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Animal bones R <input type="checkbox"/> Human bones <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Animal teeth R <input type="checkbox"/> Human teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Shells <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)	clay 40% silt 60% sand 0% <input type="checkbox"/> Granular <input type="checkbox"/> Layered <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Cohesive Compaction: <input type="checkbox"/> Hard <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Compact <input type="checkbox"/> Friable <input type="checkbox"/> Loose <input type="checkbox"/> Soft Color: <input type="checkbox"/> Black <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red <input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)

UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)

Northern Limit: Original Not Original Excavation Limit Depth: Original Not Original

Southern Limit: Original Not Original Excavation Limit

Western Limit: Original Not Original Excavation Limit

Eastern Limit: Original Not Original Excavation Limit

STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE

Is equal to:	Is bound to (only for masonry):
Is abutted by:	Abuts:
Is covered by: 1320	Covers: 1400 via Claudia, 1194
Is cut by: 1175	Cuts:
Is filled by:	Fills:

OBSERVATIONS: heavy dark brown soil over road 1400. Few artifact inclusions

DESCRIPTION
 Position within sector: along western edge, extends to southern edge
 Shape: long N-S rectangle

For layers complete this section:
 Surface (slope direction: visible inclusions): slopes to south, even E-W
 Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope) no clusters, rare inclusions
 Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?): thickens as it runs south
 Nature of the interface with layer below: sharp diffuse commingled other (specify) → clear over road, diffuse further south

For cuts complete this section:
 Cut edges: rounded straight
 Cut sides: straight concave convex sloping
 Cut bottom: flat concave irregular
 How is cut top edge? sharp rounded
 How is cut bottom edge? sharp rounded
 Observations:

1760-1

key:
 [brick pattern] = wall
 [diagonal hatching] = area being observed
 [rectangle] = blocks
 [circle] = drain pipe
 SU = 1320
 SU = extent of S. end

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)
 Size Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

Description:

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North) (section)

INTERPRETATION

This dark-brown layer is characterized by a high percentage of clay and a general paucity of artifacts, with the exception of tile which is common. SU1388 probably represents a natural post-abandonment deposit over road SU1400. It appears to have been removed from the area south of the surviving road by earlier Italian excavations.

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by T. Hart

on 8/7/11

Revised by CMH

on 18/7/11

PDFd by AMS

on 21/7/11

Entered by

on